

The Complexity OF Economic Systems

MICU Liviu Alexandru

Economics Faculty, Academy of Economic Studies, IBucharest 010374, Romania

Abstract

A theory of systems that would assume a complete mathematical classification like it was partly formulated in the case of the technical systems theory, does not exist. Despite all this, the theory of technical systems at the present offers us a good plan of attack in a practical way the complex economic systems. Old paradigms, such as interpretation and representation models of economic relations have almost exhausted their cognitive resources, no longer being able to supply relevant solutions to numerous new problems that appear inside real economical systems. After a pertinent analysis of the issues that appear inside this systems, the article offers solutions and sketches outlooks.

© 2013 AARESOC.

Keywords: economical systems, complexity, systems theory, systemic analysis

1. Introduction

A phenomenon, a context, or a complex economic system is distinguished by the fact that one cannot exactly catch its essence, as that which is complex is not entirely made of clear and distinct elements.

The Gödelian structure of economic reality ensures the permanent presence of the unknown, the unexpected, and the unpredictable. The reality levels, as a whole, have an open Gödelian structure; according to Gödel's theorem, "a rich enough axiom system leads inevitably either to non-conclusive or to contradictory results." (Guillermo, Gomez 1992)

In order to catch the complexity of economic systems, we considered two major types of approach. The economic process approach focused on the market (chrematistic), and the approach of human scale development (HSD) (in the centre of this paradigm lies a systemic re-conceptualisation of human needs, and an attempt to focus on human needs the debates regarding the development of complex economic systems). I think that, currently, the worldwide dominant approach of complex economic systems is the chrematistic one, but this is also the approach that led to the present economic crisis. In this context, I think that the chrematistic approach is "outdated" by economic reality, while the approach of human scale development is far-reaching.

2. The chrematistic approach

One of the lessons we learned from this crisis of complex economic systems is that we allowed "markets to blindly shape our economy, but in doing so, they also shaped us, and the society we live in" (Stiglitz 2010).

In its classic analysis, Polanyi (1944) emphasized that, although trade-off and chrematistic exchange date from long ago (even in prehistory), markets have always been a secondary element of wider social and cultural logic. Commerce was just one of the four main means by which human societies systematized their economic process. These were self-sufficiency (production for self consumption), reciprocity (reciprocal actions in various social groups and between them), redistribution (the product is redistributed among the group members), and commerce (chrematistics). The various development models and different societies featured a balance between these forms of economic activity organization. Still, in all societies, the logic of usability value prevailed over the chrematistic logic of exchange value.

But, during the modern age, along with the advent of the free market institution and modern capitalism, the idea of social and economic life systematization according to exclusively chrematistic reasons (the logic of exchange value) has been established, thus bringing about a radical distinction between the modern age and all the other ages.

The same *chrematistic approach* can be identified in defining and establishing modern economy. Although, in his revealing book, Smith (1961) recognised that wealth must be understood at quantitative and relational levels (that is, from the point of view of usability values), both he, and, subsequently, modern economy, shall focus their research (and the delimitation of the scope of economic studies) on *The nature and causes of the exchange values of nations* and on the way they manifest in prices, rentals, salaries and profits levels (that is, on the chrematistic dimension of complex economic systems). Non-chrematistic dimensions were considered "external" to the economic process, i.e. "exogenous variables" of economic models. Thus, the essential ecological, social, cultural, political and psychological dimensions of the "art of living and of good living" were no longer the

The development of modern market economy, and the way this *chrematistic approach* has been perceived and vested by those defining modern economy cannot be dissociated, because they mutually reflect and enhance each other. As Polanyi (1944) suggested, the central role of the market institution in the systematization of the socio-economical development process in modern age makes debates and convulsions regarding the extension of the objects of free market become a crucial political and ideological element of our modern history. Still, through the chrematistic representation of the economical process in economical theory, the debate regarding free market becomes a technical matter, which is discussed in the "scientific field" from the point of view of "economic efficiency" (rather than "chrematistic efficiency", because it is measured according to the exchange value, not from a multidimensional, systemic, *oikonomic* point of view), based on the results of various abstract models, with different initial assumptions. Thus, modelling the economic development process by means of free market appears as a purely side-aspect of superior "efficiency", not as a political matter, in which various power interests and relations collate.

This limitation of the economy to chrematistics is reflected in the way it shaped the modern idea of development, which is more and more frequently represented at coinage level, up to the point where, in practice, it is taken for chrematistic growth. Although hegemonic, this reductional conception and the study of development from a restricted, one-dimensional point of view have been keenly criticized from the beginning till now.

Among the theories criticising this approach (besides the capacities approach, which highlights the multidimensional aspects of human wealth, or ecologic economy, which criticizes the fact that wide-use economy is ignoring the biophysical base of any economic process), a fundamental early contribution to the re-conceptualisation of the notion of development from a systemic point of view, based on the usability value, is standing out, namely the approach of human scale development (HSD), discovered during the '80s.

The main concern of this research trend was to make economy subservient to population and life, not vice-versa.

3. Human scale development (HSD) in complex economic systems

"HSD appeared for the first time in an article published by the Dag Hammarskjold Foundation (DHF) in 1986." (Cruz, Stahel, Max-Neef 2009) According to Aristotle's conceptualization – where *oikonomia* had to approach not just living, but rather the "art of good living" – inside this paradigm it has been suggested that the best development process is the one that facilitates the improvement of the populations' living standard, allowing people to be coherent at their own level. The central axis of this conception is that HSD is concentrated on and sustained by satisfying man's fundamental needs, and by generating ascending autonomy levels, as well as by creating some "systemic connections between people and their environment, people and technology, the global processes and the local activity, the personal and the social, planning and autonomy, and between the civil society and the state". (Cruz, Stahel, Max-Neef 2009)

The most relevant and important postulates of this approach are shortly described in the following:

- Development refers to people, not objects. This approach implies a *theory of human needs for development*, which exceeds economic rationality, and comprises fulfilment of human needs at holistic level.
- According to Aristotle's ideas, human needs are finite. Even more, they are *few and classifiable*. For HSD, fundamental human needs are the same, no matter the culture and historical period, and they change at a very slow rate, according to our evolution as species. Needs are proposed at axiological level (they refer to things we value: subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, relaxation, creation, identity and liberty. Sometimes the need for transcendence is included. The reason is that the element changing according to era and culture does not consist of needs, but in the way these needs are satisfied or not at existential level (the meaning and the purpose of relationships for a certain person), according to the various types of existing, owning, doing things and interacting. The last ones represent the second axis along which needs manifest and are categorized during this approach. In other words, changing elements are the *satisfiers*.
- On these lines, each system of needs is satisfied or not by various types of satisfiers. These can be individual or collective, and they include all the things which, representing types of existing, possessing, doing things and interacting, contribute to satisfying human needs. *Existing* means personal or collective attributes (usually expressed by nouns associated to the intrinsic attributes of the subject, like biological composition, values, and character). *Possessing* implies institutions, norms, mechanisms, instruments, which can be expressed by one or more words (exosomatic instruments, laws, information). *Acting* suggests personal or collective actions, which can be expressed by verbs, while *interacting* means locations and environments (times, spaces), and the way people establish their own environment and integrate in it.
- Unlike needs, satisfiers are less static. They change in time and diversify according to cultures and circumstances. As a whole, satisfiers define the prevalent way a culture or a society is encompassing a need. Satisfiers may include: "organizational structures, political systems, social practices, subjective conditions, norms, values, spaces, contexts, behaviours and attitudes; all

of which are in a permanent state of tension between consolidation and change". People and societies differ from the point of view of *existence, possession, action* and *interaction*. Still, in each case, individual needs satisfaction or dissatisfaction is depending on the right combination and articulation between specific satisfiers (including between the values that make us retrospect to various satisfiers in a specific way, at individual and social level, and are themselves part of the set of satisfiers we can satisfy our needs with). From the above example we can see that, from the HSD perspective, personal and cultural values are themselves satisfiers, and they change from the chronologic and spatial point of view. They represent individual or collective attributes.

To that effect, the HSD theory is recognizing that, due to the common human nature, people must satisfy a series of fundamental needs, common for all, in order to support a rich and meaningful life. Needs may vary, because there are differences regarding the character (different types of existence, possession, action and interaction), due to factors like personality, sex, physical and psychological traits or age. These individual and group differences can change the way some needs are experienced, in specific contexts from historical and individual point of view. Still, at fundamental level, needs are experienced universally, although possibly in various proportions, due to these various attributes and personal/collective contexts.

Any unsatisfied or inappropriately satisfied human need is suggesting a form of human poverty, is preventing reaching welfare, and is generating pathologies or even deaths, due to hunger, uncertainty, social violence, suicide, or other results, depending on the type of poverty. From the HSD point of view, fundamental human needs exist according to a pre-systemic ceiling, and privation of any of the mentioned needs shall impact the whole system of needs, and, thus, the whole welfare of that person (Max-Neef, M., Elizalde, A., Hopenhyan, M., 1998). Thus, one shouldn't speak about poverty, but about *poverties*. Each person, culture or society can be rich from certain points of view, and poor from others, according to various circumstances and to the way fundamental human needs are satisfied.

Consequently, it is clear that satisfiers are not just economic means for generating goods and services in order to satisfy human needs by the aid of market. Traded goods and services are just one of the numerous categories of satisfiers. From the point of view of Aristotle's *oikonomia*, not all satisfiers (usability values) are traded or obtained on the market, thus associating them an exchange value. Many untraded (and, sometimes, untradeable) social and ecologic goods are fundamental for ensuring human subsistence and welfare. To that effect, *possession* is just one of the dimensions updating human needs, and it is necessary that complementary dimensions (*existence, action, interaction*) be equally approached and developed, by means of the adequate satisfiers. Thus, for the HSD paradigm, welfare is acting at the level of the whole system, when proper complementariness is established between various dimensions. According to Fromm's (1997) analysis, welfare cannot be limited to the sense given to it in modern culture, that of accumulation of goods and services (the *possession* dimension).

As mentioned above, in the HSD approach, needs conceptualization is based on the idea that people have multiple and interdependent needs, which interact and relate in a systemic way, and there is no bidirectional correspondence between needs and satisfiers. A satisfier can simultaneously contribute to satisfying many needs, or, on the contrary, a need can imply many satisfiers (Max-Neef, 1998). Finally, satisfiers are not neutral, but have various features, and, for analytic purposes, they are classified in five categories: destructive satisfiers, pseudo-satisfiers, inhibitor satisfiers, singular and synergic satisfiers, according to how they are associated to the whole system of needs (see Table 1). Thus, one can explain why complementariness and compensations appear during the process of satisfying the needs: choosing one satisfier to the detriment of other ones impacts how needs are satisfied at holistic level, and imposes the existence of complementary satisfiers at various levels.

Anyway, both concepts (needs and satisfiers) interact in a matrix, according to the existential and axiological features that further explain their conceptual structure and where intangible assets are not recaptured (see Table 2). The matrix has a pure illustrative goal, operating as an exemplification of the numerous elements that can be considered as satisfiers (Max-Neef, Elizalde, Hopenhyan 1998).

The matrix of needs and satisfiers represents a fundamental tool of HSD, and can be used for many goals. Through a given set of satisfiers, it helps communities and persons to become aware of their own preferences, and, even more, of the way they interact and influence each other at systemic level. By classifying and identifying satisfiers according to how they influence the various dimensions of welfare, the matrix helps to mark out how social and cultural contexts and specific development models emphasize or inhibit personal liberty, autonomy and welfare. This matrix is showing how people are satisfying their needs according to their own being and their own coherence, to those around them and to the community, and to the surrounding environment.

Table 1. The characterization of satisfiers

Type	Description
Synergic satisfier	Satisfiers which, by how they satisfy a certain need, stimulate and help to the simultaneous gratification of other needs.
Individual satisfier	This type of satisfier aims to satisfy some specific individual needs, and is neutral regarding the

	gratification of other needs.
Destructive satisfier	Elements with a paradoxical effect. Are used on the ground of satisfying a need, but they not only annihilate the possibility of satisfaction, but make impossible the appropriate satisfaction of other needs. (Sometimes they address mainly the need of protection.)
Inhibitor satisfier	Satisfiers which, by how they satisfy (generally over-satisfy) a certain need, significantly impact the possibility to satisfy other needs.
Pseudo-satisfier	Elements that stimulate a false feeling of satisfying a certain need. Although they are not as aggressive as destructive satisfiers, they can occasionally annihilate – on medium and long term – the possibility to satisfy the need initially addressed.

Source: Max-Neef, 1992

Table 2. The matrix of needs and satisfiers

Needs according to existential features	INTERACTION (spaces or atmospheres)			
	EXISTENCE (personal or collective attributes)	POSSESSION (institutions, norms, tools)	ACTION (personal or collective actions)	
Needs according to axiological features				
Subsistence	1/ Physical health, mental health, balance, sense of humour, adaptability	2/ Provisions, shelter, job	3/ Food, procreation, rest, work	4/ Life environment, social context
Protection	5/ Care, adaptability, autonomy, solidarity	6/ Insurance systems, savings, security, systems, family, job	7/ Cooperation, prevention, health care, healing, help	8/ Life space, social environment, living quarters
Affection	9/ Self-respect, respect, generosity, passion, sensuality, sense of humour	10/ Friends, partners, family, partnerships, relations with nature	11/ Making love, caressing, emotions, taking care, cultivating, appreciating	12/ Intimacy, confidentiality, home, spaces for interaction
Understanding	13/ Critical conscience, receptivity, bewilderment, intuition, rationality	14/ Curiosity, discipline, communication politics	15/ Literature, method, and analysis, meditation, interpretation	16/ Research, study, education, experiment, interaction, universities, academies, communities, family
Participation	17/ Adaptability, receptivity, determination, respect, passion, sense of humour	18/ Will, responsibilities, duties, privileges, job	19/ Rights, cooperation, sharing, obedience, agreements, expressing of opinions	20/ Affiliation, proposal, participative interaction, parties, churches, neighbourhoods, family
Relaxation	21/ Curiosity, receptivity, imagination, foolhardiness, sense of humour, lack of concerns, serenity, sensuality	22/ Games, shows, clubs, parties, peace of mind	23/ Daydreaming, procreation, dreams, memories, fantasies, recollections, relaxation, entertainment, playing	24/ Intimacy, confidentiality, spare time, neighbourhoods, landscapes
Creation	25/ Passion, determination, intuition, imagination, courage, autonomy, curiosity	26/ Competencies, method, work inventiveness,	27/ Abilities, Work, invention, construction, engineering, composition, interpretation	28/ Productive and feedback contexts, workshops, cultural groups, audiences, spaces for expression, lack of time constraints
Identity	29/ Integration, coherence, differentiation, self respect, self-assertion	30/ Language, habits,	31/ Symbols, religions, customs, confrontation,	32/ Commitment, integration, Social rhythms, daily contexts, membership context, maturation stages

		reference groups, decisions, self-roles, groups, knowledge, sexuality, values, recognition, update, norms, historic growth	
Liberty	33/ Autonomy, self respect, determination, passion, self-assertion, liberal visions, courage, rebellion, tolerance	34/ Equal rights	35/ Disagreement, 36/ Temporal/spatial choosing to be plasticity different, risk taking, awareness, commitment, disobedience, meditation

Source: Cruz, Stahel, Max-Neef 2009

The matrix of needs and satisfiers shows that complex plurality and the open unit of the levels represent two complementary dimensions of the same reality. The coexistence of these dimensions gave birth to the “reality principle: no level of reality is a privileged place, from where the other levels can be understood. A reality level is what it is due to the simultaneous existence of the other levels” (Dumitraşcu 2004).

Economic reality is not just multidimensional, but also multireferential. The economic universe acts cohesively as a whole, despite its diversity. No economic system is absolutely independent, because it is integrated as a subsystem in a higher-rank system. However large the autonomy of an economic system, it can only be a relative freedom, because the system is integrated in a superior rank system, together with other systems of the same rank.

The complexity of economic system is also emphasized by the fact that an element does not belong to a single system.

The same element simultaneously belongs to many systems.

4. The evolutionary character of economic systems and their connections

Economic entities are made of successive assemblies of elements, thus acquiring new properties, which are not found in any of the subassemblies they are made of. Economy is the result of joining a large set of economic systems, which are, in fact, subsystems of higher-rank systems. This is suggesting a high degree of economy integration and interdependence at every level, with many economic systems overlapping and linking in such a way as to induce the continuous coalescence of discontinuities and continuities, thus generating a very complex relational network.

All economic systems evolve, and during this evolution they eventually reach a state of degradation, which leads to their disappearance or replacement. The cause of this degradation is “the continuous accumulation of entropy, whose main effects are levelling and structural and functional homogenisation of the system, the major results being stagnation and loss of dynamism” (Dumitraşcu 2004).

But, before degrading, economic systems pass through a long lasting improvement process, where there are frequent changes regarding the order and organisation of elements. Thus, the importance of information organisation and adjustment is reaffirmed as the capital means for counter-balancing the degenerative ways of entropy growth.

In this context, one can affirm that the operation of economic systems takes place at the junction between two fundamental principles:

1. The principle of entropy growth, according to which the system is heading towards homogenisation and degradation
2. The principle of self-generation and self-organisation, according to which the system is perfecting its organisation and perpetuates itself.

The evolution of economic systems “is not something mystical and metaphysical, but the result of a series of qualitative changes, continuously generated by the emergence of novelty through combination and with the univocal action of the entropy law. Practically, systems evolution is the history of a continuous string of excesses, errors, compromises and expedients”.

Any economic system is integrated in a system of systems, which, in its turn, is connected to other systems of systems. In other words, economic systems can be approached both as autonomous global systems, and as partial systems, embedded as subsystems in larger systems.

Thus, the various economic systems are gradually connected based on proximity to more and more complex economic systems, creating multi-systems of multi-systems. At each integration level, the newly built systems assembly can become a meta-system, because it results from reciprocally transforming and reciprocally embedding interactions of two or more partially autonomous systems. The organisation of economic systems and multi-systems is setup so that they protect their internal field, which is why they are hierarchically structured. These hierarchies result from competitions and conflicts arising in a network-like environment, and being solved based on a relationship of dominant-dominated type.

Complex and dynamic economic systems operation cannot take place without a certain degree of disorder, noise and errors. These systems not only operate in spite of disorder, but also together with it. The existence of degenerative factors does not necessarily and always determine entropy growth; on the contrary, in certain circumstances, these factors can have many regenerating and organisational effects.

Complex economic systems or macro systems show a considerable reliability of the whole, even if their composing elements have a low reliability and can degenerate relatively easily. This is apparently a paradox, which can be explained only if the organisation of the economic process is regarded as a self-reproductive or permanent reorganisation process, by which the produced entropy is continuously eliminated from the system, and which annihilates the influence of disorganising factors from the environment.

That's why I think that, in complex economic systems, the main task of the decision maker is not so much to control disorder, but to use it in order to provide and extend order, in other words, not to obtain balance inside the system, but to control balance in motion.

5. Conclusion

Reforming complex economic systems is difficult, because it implies changing the prevailing current of thought (chrematistic approach), and "sharing similar opinions is part of the condition of social and intellectual acceptance" (Stiglitz 2010).

In my opinion, human scale development (HSD) is one of the future solutions for solving problems emerging inside complex economic systems. I think that the chrematistic approach, as a paradigm, has spent its cognitive resources, and we have to witness its gradual change, in order not to create unbalance.

Another major change to be performed is about how we, as economists, relate to human needs; here I think that the theory of human scale development is a good example to be followed.

References

- Cruz I., Stahel A., Max-Neef M. (2009). *Towards a systemic development approach: Building on the Human-Scale Development paradigm*. Ecological Economics 68 pp. 2021–2030
- Dumitraşcu, V. (2004). *Defying the complexity. Order and selforganisation in economical systems*. Editura Sedcom Libris Iaşi p. 135
- Fromm, E. (1997). *To Have or to Be?* Continuum, London.
- Georgescu, R. (1996). *The law of entropy and the economical process*. Editura Expert Bucureşti p. 344
- Guillermo, L. Gomez, M. (1992). *Intertemporal Issues Associated With The Control Of Macro-Economic Systems*. Computers Math. Applie. Vol. 24, No. 8/9, pp. 77-98
- Max-Neef, M. (1992) *Development and human needs*. In: Ekins, P., Max-Neef, M. (Eds.), *Real Life Economics*. Routledge, London, UK, pp. 197–214
- Max-Neef, M., Elizalde, A., Hopenhyan, M. (1998). *Human Scale Development. Development Dialogue*. Cepaur-Dag Hammarskjöld Foundation, Uppsala, Sweden
- Polanyi, K. (1944). *The Great Transformation*. Farrar and Rinehart, New York
- Smith, A. (1961). *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*. Methuen, London.
- Stiglitz Joseph E. (2010). *Free Fall*. Editura Publica p. 395